

Finite Element Model of Thermal Transport in Carbon Foams

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ABSTRACT

A number of carbon foam products are being developed for use as insulation, heat spreaders, and compact heat exchanger cores. The bulk properties of such a porous medium are difficult to determine analytically, particularly for the case of high concentration of non-spherical pores, or when the porous material is anisotropic or non-homogeneous. Models that predict thermal conductivity of foams often use an empirical parameter to account for the effect of pore shape and material microstructure on the conduction process. A finite element analysis has been developed to calculate the thermal conductivity of carbon foams containing micropores of different shapes. The effective thermal conductivity is then evaluated by comparing the results of the analytical and numerical models.

Keywords: carbon foam, thermal conductivity, finite element simulation, graphitic foam, pore conduction factor.

NOMENCLATURE

- K thermal conductivity [W/mK];
 K_b bulk thermal conductivity [W/mK];
 K_s solid (intrinsic) thermal conductivity [W/mK];
 K_e effective thermal conductivity of the porous medium;
 K_p thermal conductivity of pore material [W/mK];
 n pore conduction factor;
 ρ_b bulk foam density [kg/m³];
 ρ_s intrinsic density of the solid [kg/m³];
 P porosity of the porous material, $P = \frac{V_{void}}{V_{total}}$, [%];
 R relative density, $R = \frac{\rho_b}{\rho_s}$, [-];
 V_{void} volume occupied by pores [m³];
 V_{total} total volume of foam [m³];
 B constant determining the temperature field inside a pore;
 C multiplier of the dipole temperature field perturbation;
 T temperature [K];
 q_z specific heat flux in z direction (along the porous slab) [W/m²];
 ΔT temperature difference between two points on the slab [K].

INTRODUCTION

Carbon foams are a class of organic materials (Klett, [1998]) that offer significant potential for lightweight structures, for energy absorption and for thermal management. Foams can be made of metallic or non-metallic materials; they are a subset of composite materials since they are composed of gas pores contained in a continuous solid matrix. Metallic foams have been used for several decades and they have been investigated extensively. Carbon foams, however, are a new class of materials and their structure and properties are currently being studied.

Several processing methods are available for the manufacture of carbon foams. Each method can be used to create a porous material with a limited range of relative density and cell size. The resulting structure may be classified as open-celled or it may produce a structure where the majority of the cells are closed. In general, the closed-cell structure is favored for energy absorption applications while the open-celled structure is often used in thermal management, including electronics cooling.

Carbon foams can be produced with conductivities ranging from 0.1 to 200 W/mK. The conductivity is determined primarily by the degree of graphitization of the carbon in the foam, which depends on the precursor and heat treatment. The degree of graphitization is a measure of the probability of finding two layers of graphene at the same distance as in perfect crystallographic graphite. The bulk conductivity is primarily dependent on the degree of graphitization of the carbon, the volume fraction of the carbon, and the shape of the pores. High porosity (above 90% porous) foams, particularly that which is made of low conductivity carbon, conducts heat primarily by conduction in the gas pores; radiation and convection in the pores can also be significant (Gibson and Ashby, [1988]). As the solid fraction and density increases, the conduction through the solid becomes more important, especially if the solid has good thermal conductivity ($\gg 1$ W/mK).

The focus of this study is to numerically model the thermal conduction in carbon foams. Several carbon foams are being produced with pore sizes that are of the order of 100 microns, and pore walls of the order of 10 microns. An example of a foam with such micropores is shown in Fig. 1. This is a graphitic carbon foam produced at the Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL, WPAFB, Dayton, OH) with 10% solid volume fraction. It can be seen that the cells are interconnected and the typical pore size is approximately 50-100 microns.

Fig.1. Micrograph of AFRL graphitic carbon foam

Foams are a simpler subset of composite materials since the gas phase may not contribute significantly to the mechanical or transport properties. Therefore, the analysis of conduction in foams tends to be simpler than most composites. The thermal transport process in the bulk is dominated by the intrinsic thermal conductivity of the solid. The shape of pores and the total amount of porosity also influence the thermal transport. The most common method for determination of composite properties is to use the rule-of-mixtures (Chawla, [1998]). This rule considers the composite properties as volume-weighted averages of the component properties. However, when the thermal flux in the foam material is not uniform, the rule-of-mixtures is not valid. For the case of foams, the heat flow path is very tortuous; this produces additional resistance to the conduction process; therefore the bulk conductivity value is usually less than that obtained by rule-of-mixtures; the difference is often represented by an empirical “conduction parameter” that must be determined experimentally.

Analytical prediction of thermal properties of porous materials has been presented by several authors (Loeb, [1954], Bauer, [1993]). A full theoretical analysis is possible only for low porosity materials. Very high porosity (e.g. low density foams) materials are difficult to model analytically. The typical analysis for such materials tends to be semi-empirical models in which conduction, convection and radiation contributions are added (Gibson and Ashby, [1988], Glicksman, [1994]).

A comprehensive theoretical model was attempted by Bauer [1993] to predict the thermal conductivity through the porous media. In this model, analytical expressions were presented for pore distributions of any concentration, randomly oriented pores of arbitrary shape, and radiant heat transfer within the pores. However, in this model, the effect of increasing porosity and pore geometry was lumped into a semi-empirical pore shape factor (a conduction parameter) that must be known a-priori or determined experimentally. This pore shape factor is known accurately only for low porosity medium with spherical pores (Maxwell [1954]). For the case of anisotropic materials, the problem cannot be solved analytically since local thermal conductivity becomes a tensor with non-identical components that depend on the thermal conduction properties in specific directions within the material.

In this study, the focus is on developing a finite element model (FEM) of conduction transport in open and closed cell carbon foams with different levels of porosity and different pore shapes. The effect of convection and radiation within the pores will not be considered. The bulk thermal conductivity through the foam is found by finding the flux through the foam when it is subjected to a thermal gradient. The results are then compared with the analytical approach developed by Bauer [1993] and the “conduction parameter” is determined numerically for different porosity levels. The relation between the bulk thermal conductivity and the intrinsic conductivity of the solid is then evaluated in terms of this conduction parameter.

THEORY

Several models have been proposed to predict the thermal conductivity of porous materials, including foams. Thermal conductivity in foams was first studied primarily for insulating foams and several studies have discussed the thermal conductivity of insulating, high porosity foams (Gibson and Ashby [1988], Glicksman, [1994]).

In the present study, the effective thermal conductivity of the open and closed cell foams is determined by using the finite element method. The results are compared with the analytical models. For

the analysis, the relative density R will be used as a parameter. It is assumed that the mass of the voids in the foam is negligible. The relative density is then defined as:

$$R = \frac{\rho_b}{\rho_s} = 1 - \frac{P}{100} \quad (1)$$

where ρ_b is the bulk foam density, ρ_s is the intrinsic density of the solid in the foam, and P is the porosity (%) or the void content of the foam, defined as:

$$P = \frac{V_{void}}{V_{total}} \quad (2)$$

where:

V_{void} - volume occupied by pores [m^3];

V_{total} - total volume of foam [m^3].

From thermodynamic consideration, the value of thermal conductivity of a foam with non-conducting pores has a limiting value given by:

$$K_b \leq K_s \left(\frac{\rho_b}{\rho_s} \right) \quad (3)$$

The maximum value is obtained when the porous solid presents the minimum resistance to heat flow; this represents the rule of mixtures. In practice, the flow path is tortuous, and the true value is always less than the maximum predicted by Eq. (1). Several authors have used a conduction parameter termed “inefficiency factor” or “pore shape factor” to modify the equation. A factor of 2/3 has been used to correct for the flow path (Hilyard and Cunningham, [1994]). A more rigorous approach was adopted by Bauer [1993] who considered the perturbation of a continuous medium by the presence of pores. This approach will be adopted in this study. The analytical solution is obtained from the perturbation of a uniform temperature gradient in the z direction in a uniform medium due to presence of a spherical pore – this solution inside and outside the pores is given by:

$$T_{outside} = z + C \frac{z}{r^3}, \text{ and } T_{inside} = Bz \quad (4)$$

where B and C are constants that depend on the shape of the pore, and r is the radial coordinate. By solving for the temperature profile, one obtains the following differential equation for the change in the bulk thermal conductivity K_b in the porous medium as a function of porosity in the medium:

$$\frac{dK_b}{K_b} = - \frac{1 - K_p / K_b}{n + (1 - n)K_p / K_b} \frac{dV}{V} \quad (5)$$

In the above equation, K_p is the conductivity of the pores, K_b is the thermal conductivity of the bulk material that changes as the porosity increases due to increase in the total pore volume V . The new constant n is a “conduction parameter” that has a maximum value of unity. The rule of mixtures described above is represented by $n=1$.

The exponent n is obtained from the evaluation of the constants B and C , and therefore reflects the effect of the pore shape and the pore volume fraction on the thermal conduction process. Integrating the above equation from $V=0$ to the final porosity value, one obtains the following equation:

$$\frac{K_b - K_p}{K_s - K_p} \left(\frac{K_s}{K_b} \right)^{1-n} = 1 - (P/100) \quad (6)$$

We will consider the case where the solid conductivity as well as the bulk conductivity is much higher than the pore (gas) conductivity. For this special case where $K_p \ll K_b < K_s$, we obtain the following equation:

$$K_b / K_s \equiv K_e = (1 - P/100)^{1/n} = R^{1/n} \quad (7)$$

In the above equation, K_e is the effective thermal conductivity, defined here as the ratio between the bulk and solid thermal conductivity in the z direction. In the present study, the case represented by Eq. (7) will be investigated; i.e., the conduction through the pores will be neglected and all conduction will be assumed to take place through the solid.

It is important to note that the pore conduction parameter n is generally not known since it changes with pore shape and pore concentration. Therefore, this is a semi-empirical constant. When the porosity is very low, the value of n has been theoretically shown to be $2/3$ (i.e., 0.67) for spherical pores (Maxwell, [1954]). From the study carried out by Bauer [1993], the value of n for closed cell liquid foams with a porosity in the range of 60% to 95% can be calculated to be $n=0.77$. The rule of mixtures, given by $n=1$, gives the upper thermodynamic limit.

The thermal conductivity will be determined using FEM and the solution will be compared with the analytical results given by Eq. (7). The purpose of this study is to investigate the value of the pore conduction parameter n for a simple isotropic material with porosities ranging from zero to very high values (95%). The basic pore shape that will be used is a sphere; however, at high porosity level, the pores become interconnected and the pores are no longer true spheres.

FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

The finite element method is widely used to solve structural problems; and has now been adapted to the field of heat transfer analysis. To analyze the thermal field in the foam microstructure, we consider the governing differential equation of steady state heat conduction without internal heat generation in the foam. The foam piece is sandwiched between two slabs of non-porous solid as shown in Fig. 2:

Fig.2 Foam solid model

The steady-state heat conduction equation applied to the model in Fig.2 is given by:

$$\nabla \cdot (K\nabla T) = 0 \quad (8)$$

with the boundary conditions:

$$T = T_1 \text{ at the lower bottom face of the slab}$$

$$T = T_2 \text{ at the top face of the slab}$$

and $\frac{\partial T}{\partial n} = 0$ on all other surfaces.

An important step in this numerical model is to reduce computational effort by creating a unit cell of the porous medium. The unit cell that will be used to build the solid model consists of a cube with 1/8 spherical shape pores at each corner and one sphere in the middle of the cell as shown below. The foam sandwich in Fig. 2 can be constructed using combinations of unit cell shown in Fig. 3.

Fig.3 Unit cell used to model the porous medium

The solid model was analyzed by ALGOR FEM software to predict the temperature and heat flux distribution in the porous media. The solid model was first created with a specialized solid modeling software (Solid Edge) and the geometry was exported as an IGES file which was read directly into the finite element editor of ALGOR. ALGOR provides an automatic mesh generator that allows building surface and solid meshes that are either uniform or concentrated around critical regions. An unstructured four-noded tetrahedral finite element mesh (smaller mesh on the porous region) was generated over the entire domain with refinement points on the curvilinear boundaries.

For the present study, the models were meshed using a quadrilateral surface mesh and the relative size option mesh provided by ALGOR. The mesh size used for the analysis was between 15% and 25% of the smallest characteristic dimension of the model. The mesh size varied according to the void volume of the model. The higher the void volume, the smaller the mesh size since the solid dimensions become smaller with increased void volume. Using the surface mesh generated, ALGOR builds a solid mesh that consists of eight-noded bricks, tetrahedrons, pyramids and wedges. In order to increase the accuracy of the FEM solution, the mesh was refined around the spherical pores. After the mesh has been generated, the boundary conditions were applied to the mesh. This involved applying the temperature boundary conditions at the top and the bottom surface. To ensure one-dimensional heat flow along the model in z direction, boundary surfaces of the model in both x and y directions are given a symmetry (insulated) boundary condition. The other boundary condition imposed was a zero heat flux (since thermal conductivity in the gas phase is much smaller compared to the solid phase) normal to the surface of the spherical pores. As discussed earlier, conduction through the pores was expected to be negligible in this

analysis. This assumption can be relaxed in the numerical model for foams where the gas pores provide significant thermal transport.

The finite element solution of Eq. (8) is carried out over the entire domain and the temperature profile in the porous medium is determined. The heat flux in z direction, q_z , was calculate within the software. Since the heat flux at the top and bottom must be identical to the flux (per unit area of the bulk material) through the porous medium, the bulk thermal conductivity K_b is then calculated by taking the ratio of q_z to the temperature gradient in the foam.

The FEM analysis was conducted over a range of 65% to 95% porosity in the porous region, and results were obtained for spherical and ellipsoidal pores. It should be noted most carbon foams are higher than 65% in porosity. Some of the carbon foams have ellipsoidal pores that are aligned in a preferred direction. Therefore, ellipsoidal pores were included in this study along with the baseline calculations for spherical pores.

RESULTS

The temperature and heat flux distribution for a spherical pores with a total porosity of 80% are presented in the Fig. 4 and 5 below. Figure 4 shows the temperature and heat flux distribution for a unit cell from the finite element model. There is no temperature field inside the pores since the pores are assumed to be insulated.

Fig. 4 Temperature and heat flux distribution (85% porosity, spherical pores) in the unit cell

Figure 5(a) and 5(b) shows the temperature profiles for ellipsoidal pores for 85% porosity foams. In both figures the heat flux is vertical; but the pores are aligned vertically in 5(a) and horizontally in 5(b). The ratio of axes in the ellipsoidal pores is 1.35 in these figures.

Fig. 5 Temperature distribution in the foam (85% porosity, ellipsoidal pores)

The results of the finite element analysis as well as the analytical results given by Eq. (7) for different values of n are compared in Fig.6 as a function of porosity. From Fig. 6 it can be seen that, near the 100% porosity level, all solutions converge properly to the limiting values of $K_e = 0$. The solid curves are the results for spherical pores. For spherical pores, the FEM solution is lower than the rule of mixtures ($n=1$) throughout the full range of porosities. The analytical curve given by $n=0.77$ in Eq. (7) that was used by Bauer [1993], is closer to the FEM solution for a wide range of porosity; however, it produces lower value of thermal conductivity at porosities higher than 80%. It has been shown by Maxwell [1954] that, at very low values of porosity, the exponent n should have a value of 0.67 for spherical pores. Therefore, it is not possible to predict the thermal conductivity by Eq. (7) with a single value of n for the full range of porosity from 0% to 100% even when the pores are completely spherical. At 95% porosity, the value of n is calculated to be 0.853.

Fig. 6 Variation of Effective thermal conductivity with porosity

The value of the parameter n is expected to be different when the pore shape is not spherical, and when the material of the foam is not isotropic. The effect of pore shape is also shown in Fig. 6 where values for ellipsoidal pores porosity are included for three values of porosity (75%, 85% and 95%). As mentioned earlier, the ellipsoids have a ratio of 1.35 between the two major axes. The results show that the effective conductivity is higher when the major axis of the ellipsoid pores are aligned with the heat flux in the vertical direction, thereby reducing the tortuosity of the heat flux path. And as the major axis becomes longer, the result will approach the rule of mixtures. Table 1 compares the results for the cases of ellipsoidal pores and the spherical pores. As expected, the results for spherical pores lie between the two different orientations of the ellipsoid pores.

Table 1: Effective thermal conductivity for spherical and ellipsoidal pores

Porosity	Effective Conductivity K_e from numerical solution		
	Ellipsoidal Pores (Aligned with heat flux)	Spherical pores	Ellipsoidal Pores (Perpendicular to heat flux)
75%	0.232	0.2537	0.137
85%	0.1309	0.096	0.04213
95%	0.048	0.03	0.009

CONCLUSIONS

A finite element model has been used to determine the thermal conductivity of foams over the full range of porosities. The foam model was constructed by a solid modeling software using spherical and ellipsoidal pores. The thermal conductivity result was obtained in the form of a non-dimensional effective thermal conductivity. This FEM solution was then used to evaluate the “pore conduction factor” used in semi-empirical/analytical models of thermal conductivity.

The results show that a simple semi-empirical or analytical model with a constant “conduction parameter” cannot accurately predict the thermal conductivity of foams over the full range of porosity. For spherical pores, the value of this parameter increases from the theoretical value of 0.67 at low porosity to 0.85 at 95% porosity. The FEM model developed in this study can be used to model foams that are non-isotropic and non-homogeneous, with different types of pores. The effect of pore shape and non-isotropic properties will be studied in detail through this model in future work.

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